

Properties of Independent Incompatible Edges Topology on Digraphs

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Abstract

In this article, we introduce some properties of independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$ (a new topology on digraphs $\mathcal{D}$ that associates the topology with the set of edges of any directed graph $\mathcal{D}$), we investigate some properties and discuss the independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$ on a specific digraph $\mathcal{D}$, as well as the connectivity of this model of topology introduced in this article.

Introduction

Topological graph theory is an essential branch of graph theory that has a long history in mathematics. The link between topological theory and graph theory has been extensively used in many studies to induce a topology from a certain or given graph $\mathcal{G}$. Where some build models based purely on graph's nodes $\mathcal{U}$, while others build models based solely on edges $\mathcal{E}$. They are topologists who study graphs and have ramifications in almost every technical subject. Several other great fundamentals on graph theory mathematics, topological graph theory with some main applications, readers may be found it in. [1-7].

The graphs are assorted into two main species: directed or undirected graphs. Some academics fasten a topological space with an undirected graph. Jafarian et al. in 2013, coupled the vertex set $\mathcal{U}$ of any locally finite graph without isolated vertex with a Graphic Topology [8]. In 2018, Kilicman and Abdulkalek found that any basic graph with isolated vertex has an Incidence Topology on a set of vertices $\mathcal{U}$ [9]. Asmhan and Zainab link a topology to the vertex set $\mathcal{U}$ of any undirected graph, which can have one or more isolated vertices [10]. Independent Topology was introduced in 2020 as a new definition of the family of Sub-basis as a set of all vertices which are non-adjacent to the vertex $\emptyset$. The same authors also found a link between a tritopological space and an undirected graph, or three different topologies formed by a single graph. They named IVIG-Induced Topological Space [11] after the three topologies mentioned above (Independent Topology, Incidence Topology, and Graphic Topology), and they introduced the topology's separation axioms in [12].

In the directed graph, Bhargava and Ahlborn [13] in 1968 proved that each directed graph defines a unique (topology) topological space. In 1972, Lieberman [14] was defined two topologies on the set of nodes $\mathcal{U}$ of every directed graph called the left topology and the right topology. In 2010, Marijun [15] was studied the relations between finite topology and directed graph. All these previous papers of topologies on digraphs were associated with the nodes set $\mathcal{U}$, until now there are a very few works associated a topology with the set of edges $\mathcal{E}$ of a certain digraph, as in [16] by Abdulkalek and Kilicman. This motivated Asmhan F. H and Zainab R. Z in 2021, to introduced the independent compatible edges topology [17], they were defined it as a topology associated with the edge $\mathcal{S}$ of edges $\mathcal{E}$ of the digraph $\mathcal{D}$ (s.t. if $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{f} \in \mathcal{B}$, $\mathcal{f}$ is non-adjacent edge with $\mathcal{S}$ in the same direction and $\mathcal{f}$ construct with $\mathcal{S}$ a path of length three) and the basic steps toward studying some important results and main properties of that topology introduced in [18].

Also in 2021, Asmhan F. H and I. A. Ali introduced the independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$ [19], which defined as a topology associated with the edge $\mathcal{S}$ of edges $\mathcal{E}$ of the digraph $\mathcal{D}$ (such that if $\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{f} \in \mathcal{B}$, $\mathcal{f}$ is non-adjacent edge with $\mathcal{S}$ in the different direction and $\mathcal{f}$ construct with $\mathcal{S}$ a path of length three).

In this article, the features and qualities (properties) of independent incompatible edges topology were studied. On this topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$, some preliminary connection results were also examined.

Section 2 includes some main definitions of topology and graph theory and the definition of independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$. Section 3 introduces the independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$ properties on the set of edges $\mathcal{E}$ of directed graphs $\mathcal{D}$. The fourth section contains preliminary results on the connectivity of independent incompatible edges topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$. Finally, in the concluding section of this

article some conclusions about independent incompatible edges topology qualities and connectivity are presented.

1. PRELIMINARIES

This section introduces graph theory and topology with some basic definitions and preliminaries. All of these concepts are widely used and may be found in books like [2] [3] [19].

A directed graph is employed in the majority of situations. $\mathcal{D}$ is made up of a set $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{D})$ of non-empty nodes, a set $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D})$ of directed arcs, and an incidence $\mathcal{D}$ that relates each of $\mathcal{D}$'s arcs to an ordered pair of nodes (not necessarily different). A digraph is usually denoted by $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{D})$. If $(\mathfrak{Z})=(u, \wp)$, then u is the starting and $\wp$ is the ending vertices of $\mathfrak{Z}$, and $\mathfrak{Z}$ is also an arrow connecting u , and $\wp$. The line $\mathfrak{Z}$ is referred to be a self-loop if $(\mathfrak{Z})=(\wp,\wp)$. Two (or more) directed edges with the same beginning and ending vertex are called parallel. Adjacent edges are two different edges that cross at a one common vertex. A digraph with no parallel edges and loops is referred to as a simple digraph. In a simple digraph $\mathcal{D}$, a complete symmetric digraph is where every vertex has precisely one edge directed to every other vertex. A directed path is an interchanging series of unique vertices and unique arcs that starts and ends with vertices. A directed cycle is a directed path starts and stops at the same vertex. A directed cycle graph is a digraph that is made up of just one directed cycle.

$\mathbb{K}_n, \mathbb{K}_{n_1, n_2}, \mathbb{C}_n,$ and $\mathbb{P}_m$ are the notations we utilize where $\mathbb{K}_n$ a complete digraph with n nodes, $\mathbb{K}_{n_1, n_2}$ the complete bipartite digraph where partite sets have sizes n_1 and n_2 , $\mathbb{C}_n$ the cycle digraph on n nodes, and $\mathbb{P}_m$ the path on m arcs.

A topology $\mathbb{T}$ on a non-empty set $\mathbb{X}$ is a combination of open subsets of $\mathbb{X}$ which satisfy: $\emptyset, \mathbb{X} \in \mathbb{T}, \mathbb{M} \cap \mathbb{N} \in \mathbb{T}$ fore every $\mathbb{M}, \mathbb{N} \in \mathbb{T}, \cup_{\alpha \in \Delta} \mathbb{N}_\alpha \in \mathbb{T}$ for every sub-combination $\mathbb{N}_\alpha$ of $\mathbb{T}$. Then $(\mathbb{X}, \mathbb{T})$ is called a topological space and $\mathbb{N}$ a sub-set of $\mathbb{X}$ is named an open set if $\mathbb{N} \in \mathbb{T}$. If $\mathbb{T} = \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{X})$ on $\mathbb{X}$ is referred to as discrete topology however $\mathbb{T} = \{\emptyset, \mathbb{X}\}$ on $\mathbb{X}$ is referred to as indiscrete topology.

Now **the independent incompatible edges topology we defined it as:** Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$ be any digraph. The independent incompatible edges topology, denote $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$, is a topology that associated with the set $\mathcal{E}$ of edges of $\mathcal{D}$ and induced by the sub-basis $\mathcal{S}_{IE}$ whose elements consist of the sets: $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{E}, |\mathcal{B}| \leq 2$ such that if $\mathfrak{Z}, \mathfrak{f} \in \mathcal{B}, \mathfrak{f}$ is non-adjacent with $\mathfrak{Z}$ in the different direction and $\mathfrak{f}$ construct with $\mathfrak{Z}$ a path of length three.

3. Properties of Independent Incompatible edges topologies

Proposition 3.1: Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$ be a digraph, $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ be the independent incompatible edges of topology of $\mathcal{D}$. Then the following statements are satisfied:

- i. If $\mathbb{L} = \{\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathcal{E} : |A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z})| \geq 2 \text{ or } A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z}) = \emptyset\} \rightarrow \mathbb{L} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$.
- ii. If $\mathbb{F} = \{\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathcal{E} : |A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z})| = 1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$ is closed set in $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$.

Proof:

- i. Let $\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathbb{L}$, since $|A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z})| \geq 2$ or $A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z}) = \emptyset \rightarrow \mathbb{U}_{II}(\mathfrak{Z}) = \{\mathfrak{Z}\}$ (by using remark in [19]). Then we have $\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathbb{U}_{II}(\mathfrak{Z}) \subseteq \mathbb{L} \rightarrow \mathfrak{Z}$ is an interior point of $\mathbb{L}$. Hence $\mathbb{L}$ open, i.e., $\mathbb{L} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$.
- ii. To prove $\mathbb{F}$ is closed in $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$, i.e., to prove $\mathbb{F}^c$ is open. Since $\mathbb{F} = \{\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathcal{E} : |A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z})| = 1\}$ (by hypothesis). So $\mathbb{F}^c = \{\mathfrak{Z} \in \mathcal{E} : |A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z})| \geq 2 \text{ or } A_{II}(\mathfrak{Z}) = \emptyset\}$, then by (i) $\mathbb{F}^c \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$. Hence $\mathbb{F}$ is closed in $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$. (a subset of any topological space is closed if it's complement is open) (See [20]).

Definition 3.2: $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$ is a digraph. $\mathcal{W}$ is considered a sub-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$ if all of the nodes and edges of $\mathcal{D}$ are in $\mathcal{D}$, $\mathcal{W}$ is $\mathcal{D}$'s limitation to $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{W})$. Edges-induced sub-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$ is a subset of the edges of $\mathcal{D}$ plus any nodes that serve as their endpoints. (See [21]).

Definition 3.3: $\mathcal{W}$ is any edge- induced sub-digraph of a digraph $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$. The independent incompatible edges topology of $\mathcal{W}$ denoted by $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$, which is associated with the set $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$ (edges of $\mathcal{W}$) and induced by the sub-basis $\mathcal{S}_{IE}$ whose elements such as: $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, |\mathcal{B}| \leq 2$ s.t if $\mathfrak{Z}, \mathfrak{g} \in \mathcal{E}$ is non- adjacent with $\mathfrak{Z}$ by a different direction, and $\mathfrak{g}$ create with $\mathfrak{Z}$ a path of length three.

Any subset of any topological space has the standard topology defined below. (See [21])

Definition 3.4: $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$ is a digraph, $\mathcal{W} = (\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{W}}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \varphi \mathcal{W})$ is an edge-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$. The topological $\mathcal{T}_{IE} |_{\mathcal{W}}$ is an independent incompatible edge topology of $\mathcal{W}$ with respect to $\mathcal{D}$ such that $\mathcal{T}_{IE} |_{\mathcal{W}} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}} \cap \mathbb{U} : \mathbb{U} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})\}$.

Example 3.2.5: $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi \mathcal{D})$ is a directed graph shown in Figure 1, $\mathcal{W} = (\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{W}}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \varphi \mathcal{W})$ be an edge-induced sub-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$, such that, $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{W}) = \{\wp_1, \wp_2, \wp_3, \wp_4\}, \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{W}) = \{\mathfrak{Z}_1, \mathfrak{Z}_2, \mathfrak{Z}_3, \mathfrak{Z}_5\}$ and $\varphi \mathcal{W}(\mathfrak{Z}_1) = (\wp_1, \wp_2), \varphi \mathcal{W}(\mathfrak{Z}_2) = (\wp_2, \wp_3), \varphi \mathcal{W}(\mathfrak{Z}_3) = (\wp_4, \wp_3), \varphi \mathcal{W}(\mathfrak{Z}_5) = (\wp_1, \wp_4)$.

$\mathcal{D}\mathcal{W}$

Figure 1. $\mathcal{W}$ is a sub-digraph of a digraph $\mathcal{D}$

Sub-basis for $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$ is given by

$$\mathcal{S}_{IE\mathcal{W}} = \{\{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_5\}\}.$$

By taking intersection finitely, the basis obtained is $\{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_2\}, \emptyset$.

Then by taking all unions the topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$ can be written as:

$$\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W}) = \{\emptyset, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_5\}\}.$$

And $\mathcal{S}_{IE} = \{\{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_4\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_5\}\}$.

By taking intersection finitely, the basis obtained is

$$\{\mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_2\}, \emptyset.$$

Then by taking all unions the topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ can be as:

$$\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D}) = \{\emptyset, \mathcal{E}, \{\mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_5\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_4\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_5\}\}.$$

Now, $\mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}} = \{\emptyset, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \{\mathcal{S}_2\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_3\}, \{\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_5\}, \{\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3\}\}$.

We show that $\mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}} \neq \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$.

Always $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W}) \subseteq \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$ and this is lucid in the following proposition.

Proposition 3.6. Let $\mathcal{W}$ be an edges-induced sub-digraph of digraph $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi\mathcal{D})$. Then we always $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W}) \subseteq \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$.

Proof: Let $\mathbb{M} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$, so that $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$. To prove $\mathbb{M} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$ i.e., we need to prove $\mathbb{M} = \mathbb{M}^* \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$ for some $\mathbb{M}^* \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$.

We put $\mathbb{M} = \mathbb{U} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$ such that $\mathbb{U} = \bigcap \{\mathbb{H} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D}) : \mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{H}\}$

$\rightarrow \mathbb{U} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ (since $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is an Alexandoff space).

It is clear that $\mathbb{M} \subseteq \mathbb{U} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$ -----(1)

Let $\varphi \in \mathbb{U} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}} \rightarrow \exists \mathcal{S} \in \mathbb{M}$ s.t $\mathcal{S}$ create with φ a path of length three in $\mathcal{W}$. So, there is an open set $\mathbb{B} \in \mathcal{S}_{IE\mathcal{W}}$ such that $\mathbb{B} = \{\mathcal{S}, \varphi\}$ (by definition of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$).

Since $\mathbb{B}$ is the smallest open set contain $\{\mathcal{S}, \varphi\}$, then $\mathbb{B} \subseteq \mathbb{M}$ and thus $\varphi \in \mathbb{M}$. So $\mathbb{U} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}} \subseteq \mathbb{M}$ -----(2).

By (1) and (2) we get $\mathbb{M} = \mathbb{U} \cap \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}$.

Hence $\mathbb{M} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$. $\square$

Remark 3.7. $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi\mathcal{D})$ is a directed graph, $\mathcal{W} = (\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{W}}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \varphi\mathcal{W})$ be an edge-induced sub-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$, edges of $\mathcal{W}$ are called preserve non-adjacency w. r. t. $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ if $|A_{II}(\mathcal{S})| \geq 2$ in $\mathcal{D}$, then $|A_{II}(\mathcal{S})| \geq 2$ in $\mathcal{W}$ for every $\mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{W}$.

Now, the two topologies $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W})$ and $\mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$ on $\mathcal{W}$ are the same. We will see that in the following;

Proposition 3.8. $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi\mathcal{D})$ is a directed graph, $\mathcal{W} = (\mathcal{U}_{\mathcal{W}}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}}, \varphi\mathcal{W})$ be an edge-induced sub-digraph of $\mathcal{D}$.

Then: -

Edges of $\mathcal{W}$ are preserve non-adjacency $\Rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W}) \subseteq \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$.

Proof: -

Let the all edges of $\mathcal{W}$ are preserve non-adjacency, then $\exists \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{W}$ such that $|A_{II}(\mathcal{S})| \geq 2$ in $\mathcal{D}$ and $|A_{II}(\mathcal{S})| \geq 2$ in $\mathcal{W}$.

So, $\{\mathcal{S}\} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ (by using proposition in [19]).

But $\mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{W}} \cap \mathbb{U} : \mathbb{U} = \{\mathcal{S}\} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})\}$, and (by using proposition 3.6.). We get $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{W}) \subseteq \mathcal{T}_{IE}|_{\mathcal{W}}$. $\square$

Definition 3.9. Let $\mathcal{D}_1 = (\mathcal{U}_1, \mathcal{E}_1, \varphi\mathcal{D}_1)$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = (\mathcal{U}_2, \mathcal{E}_2, \varphi\mathcal{D}_2)$ are two directed graphs. We summons $\mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2$ are isomorphic to each other, and written $\mathcal{D}_1 \cong \mathcal{D}_2$, if there exist bijective functions $\Omega : \mathcal{U}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{U}_2$ and $\Phi : \mathcal{E}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{E}_2$ s. t. $\mathcal{S}$ is a directed edge from ϱ to γ in $\mathcal{D}_1$ iff $\Phi(\mathcal{S})$ is a directed edge from $\Omega(\varrho)$ to $\Omega(\gamma)$ in $\mathcal{D}_2$. The maps Ω and Φ are called isomorphisms. (See [2])

Remark 3.10. If the digraphs $\mathcal{D}_1 = (\mathcal{U}_1, \mathcal{E}_1, \varphi\mathcal{D}_1)$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = (\mathcal{U}_2, \mathcal{E}_2, \varphi\mathcal{D}_2)$ are **isomorphic** then the topological spaces $(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_{IE_1}(\mathcal{D}_1))$ and $(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_{IE_2}(\mathcal{D}_2))$ are **homeomorphic**, however the opposite is not always true in broadly.

Example 3.11. Let $\mathcal{D}_1 = (\mathcal{U}_1, \mathcal{E}_1, \varphi\mathcal{D}_1)$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = (\mathcal{U}_2, \mathcal{E}_2, \varphi\mathcal{D}_2)$ are two directed graphs shown in the figure 2. It is clear that $\mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2$ isomorphic, so $\mathcal{T}_{IE_1}$ and $\mathcal{T}_{IE_2}$ are homeomorphic.

Figure 2. Two digraphs $\mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2$ are isomorphic

Example 3.12. Let $\mathcal{D}_1 = (U_1, \mathcal{E}_1, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}_1})$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = (U_2, \mathcal{E}_2, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}_2})$ are two directed graphs shown in the figure 3. It is clear that $\mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2$ are not isomorphic, but $\mathcal{T}_{IE_1}$ and $\mathcal{T}_{IE_2}$ are homomorphic in order that both are discrete topologies.

Figure 3. Two digraphs $\mathcal{D}_1$ and $\mathcal{D}_2$ are not isomorphic.

Remark 3.13.[6] If $\Psi: (\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_1) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_2)$ is a function between two topological spaces then:

- 1) Ψ is continuous $\Leftrightarrow \Psi(\overline{Y}) \subseteq \overline{\Psi(Y)} \forall Y \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1$.
- 2) Ψ is closed $\Leftrightarrow \overline{\Psi(Y)} \subseteq \Psi(\overline{Y})$.

Proposition 3.14. Let $\mathcal{D}_1 = (U_1, \mathcal{E}_1, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}_1})$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = (U_2, \mathcal{E}_2, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}_2})$ are two directed graphs. $\mathcal{T}_{IE_1}(\mathcal{D}_1)$ and $\mathcal{T}_{IE_2}(\mathcal{D}_2)$ be an independent incompatible edges topology of D_1 and D_2 ,

Ψ is a function between $(\mathcal{E}_1, \mathcal{T}_{IE_1}(\mathcal{D}_1))$ and $(\mathcal{E}_2, \mathcal{T}_{IE_2}(\mathcal{D}_2))$. S.t. $\Psi: \mathcal{E}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{E}_2$. Then: 1. Ψ is continuous $\Leftrightarrow A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\} \rightarrow A_{II}(\Psi(\varrho)) = \{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\} \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1$.

2. If Ψ is onto and $A_{II}(\Psi(\varrho)) = \{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\} \rightarrow A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\} \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1$, then Ψ is closed.

For the converse, if Ψ is one-to-one and closed $\rightarrow A_{II}(\Psi(\varrho)) = \{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}$ implies $A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\} \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1$.

Proof:

1. Since $A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\} \Leftrightarrow \varrho \in \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}} \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1$ (by using corollary in [19])

So, we must prove that Ψ is continuous $\Leftrightarrow \varrho \in \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}} \rightarrow \Psi(\varrho) \in \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}}$

Let Ψ is continuous and $\varrho \in \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}} \rightarrow \Psi(\varrho) \in \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}}$ -----(1)

But the, $\Psi(\overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}}) \subseteq \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}}$ (since Ψ is continuous) -----(2)

So, by (1) and (2) we get $\Psi(\varrho) \in \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}}$.

The converse, suppose $\varrho \in \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}}$ implies $\Psi(\varrho) \in \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}}$ to prove Ψ is continuous.

Let $\mathbb{H}$ be a subset of $\mathcal{E}_1$ and $\varrho \in \overline{\mathbb{H}}$. It is clear that $\mathbb{H} = \cup_{\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{H}} \{\mathfrak{S}\}$ and so

$\overline{\mathbb{H}} = \overline{\cup_{\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{H}} \{\mathfrak{S}\}} = \cup_{\mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{H}} \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}}$ (by using the properties of closure) (see [21]).

And for this reason, $\exists \mathfrak{S} \in \mathbb{H}$ s.t. $\varrho \in \overline{\{\mathfrak{S}\}}$.

Also, according to the hypothesis $\Psi(\varrho) \in \overline{\{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}} \subseteq \overline{\Psi(\mathbb{H})}$. Therefore $\overline{\Psi(\mathbb{H})} \subseteq \overline{\Psi(\overline{\mathbb{H}})}$ and hence Ψ is continuous.

2. If Ψ is onto (surjective), assume that Ω is a right inverse of Ψ and $A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\}$.

Then $A_{II}(\Psi(\Omega(\varrho))) = \{\Psi(\Omega(\mathfrak{S}))\}, \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_2$ and since $(\Psi \circ \Omega = id_{\mathcal{E}_2}) \cdot A_{II}(\Omega(\varrho)) = \{\Omega(\mathfrak{S})\}$ (by assumptions) $\rightarrow \Omega$ is continuous (by using (1) above).

So, if $\mathbb{F}$ is closed and $\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_1$ and since Ω is continuous then $\Psi(\mathbb{F}) = \Omega^{-1}(\mathbb{F})$ that is closed.

On converse, if Ψ is one-to-one and closed $\rightarrow \Psi^{-1}$ is continuous on $\Psi(\mathcal{E}_1)$.

So $A_{II}(\Psi(\varrho)) = \{\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\},$ (by (1)) $\forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1$

$\rightarrow A_{II}(\Psi^{-1}(\Psi(\varrho))) = \{\Psi^{-1}(\Psi(\mathfrak{S}))\}$.

Hence $A_{II}(\varrho) = \{\mathfrak{S}\} \forall \varrho, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}_1. \square$

4. Connectivity of Independent Incompatible Edges Topology

This section looks at and describes the requirements and conditions for connection in a topology with independent incompatible edges.

Definition 4.1. *Connected space* is a topological space that can't be described as the union of any two or more nonempty open subsets. (See [21])

Definition 4.2. $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$ is a directed graph. The topology $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ of a set $\mathcal{E}$ is connected if $\mathcal{E}$ is not the union $\mathcal{E} = \mathbb{H}_1 \cup \mathbb{H}_2$ such that $\mathbb{H}_1$ and $\mathbb{H}_2$ are non-empty open subsets that are disjoint.

Remark 4.3. $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$ is a directed graph.

1) By using corollary in [19], the independent incompatible edge topology of $\mathcal{D}$ such that $|\mathbb{A}_{II}(\mathfrak{S})| \geq 2$ or $\mathbb{A}_{II}(\mathfrak{S}) = \emptyset \forall \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}$ is disconnected since it is discrete topology.

2) if $|\mathbb{A}_{II}(\mathfrak{S})| = 1$ for any $\mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{E}$ then an independent incompatible edge topology of $\mathcal{D}$ is not discrete topology, therefore it is disconnected.

Proposition 4.4. If $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$ be disconnected digraph, then $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is disconnected.

Proof: Suppose $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$ be a disconnected directed graph. So $\mathcal{D}$ has two or more than two connected components (connected sub-digraph).

Let $\{\mathcal{D}_{\delta}, \delta \in \Delta\}$ is represent a set of all the components of $\mathcal{D}$ s.t. $\mathcal{D}_{\delta} = (\mathcal{U}_{\delta}, \mathcal{E}_{\delta}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}_{\delta}})$ Then $\bigcup_{\mathcal{B}_i \in \mathcal{S}_{IE_{\delta}}} \mathcal{B}_i = \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta}) \forall \mathcal{D}_{\delta}, \delta \in \Delta$ and all $\mathcal{B}_i \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$

$\forall \mathcal{B}_i \in \mathcal{S}_{IE_{\delta}}$, so that $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta}) \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ -----(1)

Now since $[\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})]^c$ is the union of all other components edges i.e.

$[\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})]^c \subseteq \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D})$, so $[\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})]^c \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ -----(2)

But the $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}) = \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta}) \cup [\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})]^c$.-----(3)

Thus by (1), (2) and (3) we have $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D})$ is the union of any two non-empty open disjoint subsets $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})$ and $[\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}_{\delta})]^c$.

Therefore $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is disconnected (by using definition 4.2). $\square$

Remark 4.5. In general, the antithesis of proposition 4.4 is not true. Accordingly in example: Let $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$ be the complete symmetric digraph $\mathbb{K}_3$, it has disconnected $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ but digraph $\mathbb{K}_3$ is connected digraph.

Proposition 4.6. For any connected digraph $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$. If $\exists \mathcal{g} \in \mathcal{E}$ s.t. $\mathbb{A}_{IE}(\mathcal{g}) = \emptyset$, then $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is disconnected.

Proof: Let $\mathbb{A}_{IE}(\mathcal{g}) = \emptyset$ for any $\mathcal{g} \in \mathcal{E} \rightarrow \{\mathcal{g}\} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ ((by using proposition in [19]) ----(1)

Since $\mathcal{E} = \bigcup_{\mathcal{B}_i \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}} \mathcal{B}_i$ s.t. $i \geq 1$ (by definition of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$)

So, $\mathcal{E} - \{\mathcal{g}\} \in \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ (by definition of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$). -----(2)

But the $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D}) = \{\mathcal{g}\} \cup \mathcal{E} - \{\mathcal{g}\}$ -----(3)

So, by (1), (2) and (3) we obtain that; $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{D})$ is the union of any two non-empty open disjoint subset.

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is disconnected topology (by using definition 4.2). $\square$

Remark 4.7. In general, the antithesis of proposition 4.6 is not always true. Accordingly, for example the complete bipartite digraph $\mathbb{K}_{2,2}$ has a disconnected $\mathcal{T}_{IE}$ but, there is no an edge $\mathcal{g}$ in the complete bipartite digraph $\mathbb{K}_{2,2}$ s.t. $\mathbb{A}_{IE}(\mathcal{g}) = \emptyset$

Proposition 4.8. If $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D}))$ is a topological space of any connected digraph $\mathcal{D} = (\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E}, \varphi_{\mathcal{D}})$. Then $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D}))$ is connected $\Leftrightarrow$ intersection of two distinct sets in the family of sub-basis $\mathcal{S}_{IE}$ of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ is not an empty.

Proof: $\Rightarrow$ suppose the space $(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D}))$ is connected.

$\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{E}$ is not the union $\mathcal{E} = \mathbb{H}_1 \cup \mathbb{H}_2$ such that $\mathbb{H}_1$ and $\mathbb{H}_2$ are non-empty open disjoint subsets (by definition 4.2).

$\Leftrightarrow \forall \mathbb{V}_i, \mathbb{V}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}$ of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$ (by using the definition of $\mathcal{T}_{IE}(\mathcal{D})$) s.t for some i, j $(\bigcup_{\mathbb{V}_i \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}} \mathbb{V}_i) \cap (\bigcup_{\mathbb{V}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}} \mathbb{V}_j) = \mathcal{E}$ and $(\bigcup_{\mathbb{V}_i \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}} \mathbb{V}_i) \cap (\bigcup_{\mathbb{V}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}} \mathbb{V}_j) = \emptyset$

$\Leftrightarrow \mathbb{V}_i \cap \mathbb{V}_j \neq \emptyset$ for all $\mathbb{V}_i, \mathbb{V}_j \in \mathcal{S}_{IE}$ s.t. $\mathbb{V}_i \neq \mathbb{V}_j$. $\square$

Conclusions

We present a study of attributes for topologies with independent incompatible edges (topology on directed graphs by associating a topology with the set of edge). Some of the topology's properties were investigated in-depth on a few digraphs. Because the independent incompatible edges topology offers all directed paths in the directed graph, the new topology can tackle various problems on weighted directed graphs that focus on directed paths, which can be regarded as one of our recommendations for future work.

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